

Human Skill: An Emerging Dimension of Social Media and Competitive Advantage in Sri Lankan Hotel Industry

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Abstract:

Having good human skills gives the ability to get the best out of their people. The employees' IT skill is increasingly common utilization of social media in hotel industry. Utilizing the social media as a marketing strategy, hoteliers can ensure their advantage in competitive market. As such, the purpose of this paper is to study the relationship between human skill and social media and also the relationship between human skill and competitive advantage. The primary data for this research were collected through survey questionnaire. The questionnaire is designed using structured questions to measure the relationship among the variables. Correlation values and Parameter estimate; multivariate data analysis were employed to test the hypotheses. The results of this paper indicate that the high positive relationship between human skill and utilization of social media. Also, the results give the high positive relationship between human skill and competitive advantage in Sri Lankan hotel industry

Keywords: Sri Lankan hotel industry, human skill, Social media, competitive advantage.

INTRODUCTION

Many individuals and organizations tend to use the social media for communication interactively and it has become a part of our lives. Professional marketers have changed their approach to consumer engagement because they no longer trust advertising in the way of traditional methods of marketing. Also, only the creative and innovative suppliers would be able to survive in the competition in the new millennium. Hence, the information technologies change the competitive advantages for almost all organizations (Patil et al., 2015; Ruth et al., 2015).

The arrival of social media as a modern marketing technique has massively changed the way of communication in the firm with customers. With massive number of users worldwide the social media can be use as a strategic marketing technique to service providers, including the hotel industry. The social media channels allows to shearing information in each other in which customers to take a more active role as market players and reach almost everyone anywhere and anytime (Hennig-Thurau et al., 2010).

ROLE OF HUMAN SKILL FOR SOCIAL MEDIA IN HOTEL INDUSTRY

Human skills can be defined as an ability to work well with others both individually and in group (www.accounting4management.com/human_skills). These skills are equally important for the lower level, middle level and top level management. Managers would have to deal directly with people. They are required to know how to communicate, motivate, lead, and inspire enthusiasm and trust (www.accounting4management.com/human_skills). According to Kotler and Armstrong, 2010, marketing means managing profitable customer relationships. The most important objective of marketing is to attract new customers by promising superior customer satisfaction and value. It is crucial for companies to truly understand the consumer's needs because a product that provides superior customer value is easier to sell to the consumers (Kotler and Armstrong, 2010).

Hotel facilities are to be facilitated at higher prices compared with other competitors such as from Malaysia, Thailand, Vietnam etc. (Lankadeepa Newspaper discussion with Chairman of Tourist Hotel Committee meeting, Jayathissa Kehelpannala, 03.11.2013). The study was concerns with the new ICT, in particularly the

social media and their role in knowledge acquisition and sharing by and among the tourism actors who may help to increase direct marketing through the social media. The hotel industry in Sri Lanka has the potentials to use social media to popularize their product and services among the European and American population. As the usage of social media is high among the populations in Europe and America (Case and King (2013).

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

To meet the objectives, this analytical research examined the following hypotheses: (i) there is a relationship between human skill and social media. (ii) There is a relationship between human skill and competitive advantage.

RESEARCH METHODS

Survey Instrument

The researcher developed a standard questionnaire to measure the all variables that are relevant to the study by adapting existing scales. The questionnaire was close ended and the respondents rated their agreement with each item on a Likert scale ranging from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5). To gather information on the variable semi structure interviews were also used. A five-point Likert scale was used with anchor from 1= “Strongly disagree” to 5= “strongly agree at all”.

Sampling and data collection

This study considered the main sample size as 331 respondents with assessment of construct validity and testing the reliability. The sample for this study came from star grade hotels in Sri Lanka undertaking executive grade offices. Using a universal sampling, each manager was invited to participate in the survey. Upon obtaining respondent’s consent, he/she was asked to complete the self-administered questionnaire. The questionnaires were distributed among the 392 executive officers of star hotels in the period of May to December, 2014 in Sri Lanka. Journals, publications, magazines, and books accessed via the Internet are the main sources of secondary data for this study

Data Analysis

Data was analyzed through the SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) for which the descriptive frequency analysis, Pearson Product Moment Correlation, and Parameter estimate in General Linear Multivariate analysis.

RESULTS

Human Skill

The measurement model of the human skill (HS) was analyzed using the two proposed factors top management commitment (TC) and IT knowledge and experiences (ITK). All these two factors of human skill were considered as independent variables in this study. In total, 8 items represented the two factors of HS subject to EFA analysis.

Figure: 1 - Association between Human Skill with Social Media and Competitive Advantage

Competitive advantages as a dependent variable where it was measured by the two variables of customer satisfaction (CS) and organizational performance (OP). Social media utilization is also the dependent variable

of this conceptual framework. Following the resource-based theory, human resource is positively influencing the firm’s competitive advantage which should also be considered strategic as other resources (Olalla, 1999).

Figure: 2 - Association between Human Skill and its Dimensions

(I) There is a relationship between human skill and competitive advantage.

Table 1: Testing Hypotheses using Parameter Estimates

Dependent V.	Parameter	B	Std. Error	t	Sing
CSC	ITK	.387	.059	6.528	.000
CST	TMC	.115	.040	2.886	.004
CSD	TMC	.213	.057	3.753	.000
CSD	ITK	.181	.051	3.525	.000
OPI	ITK	.127	.046	2.741	.006
OPM	ITK	.111	.041	2.683	.008
OPC	TMC	.139	.056	2.493	.013
OPC	ITK	.470	.050	9.339	.000

The GLM findings shows that the parameter estimates are .387 and .181 the p-value is <.05, thus the result is significant for IT knowledge and experience with communication and distribution of the customer satisfaction respectively. Furthermore, IT knowledge and experience has a positive influence with internal factors ($\beta = .127$, $p < .05$), market factors ($\beta = .111$, $p < .05$) and competitive factors ($\beta = .470$, $p < .05$) of the organizational performance.

Top management commitment as a measurement of the human skill variable, it make a positive relationship with the transaction and distribution of customer satisfaction ($\beta = .115$, $p < .05$, $\beta = .213$, $p < .05$). Furthermore, there is a positive relationship between top management commitment and competitive factors of organizational performance ($\beta = .139$, $p < .05$). Therefore, the study shows that human skill has a statistically significant positive impact on the competitive advantages. Thus, H1 is supported by the data.

II) There is a relationship between human skill and social media.

Table 2: Testing Hypotheses using Parameter Estimates

Dependent Variable	Parameter	B	Std. Error	t	Sing
SMO	TMC	0.174	0.0555	3.1321	0.002
	ITK	0.505	0.0501	10.0829	0.000
SMS	ITK	0.920	0.0243	37.8428	0.000
SMP	ITK	0.611	0.0372	16.4137	0.000

The GLM findings show that the parameter estimate is .174 and the p-value is <.05, thus the result is significant for the top management commitment and openness of the social media. Furthermore, IT knowledge and

experience make a positive influence with the openness of the social media ($\beta = .505$, $p < .05$), shearing of the social media ($\beta = .920$, $p < .05$) and also the peering of the social media ($\beta = .611$, $p < .05$). Therefore, the study shows that human skill has a statistically significant positive impact on the social media utilization. Thus, H2 is supported by the data.

DISCUSSION

This research examines the relationship between the human skill and social media utilization. As might be expected, human skill was found to be a significant determinant for the social media utilization as measured by IT knowledge and top management commitment. The findings of this study emphasized that IT knowledge; top management commitments have a moderate positive relationship with the social media utilization in star hotels. Furthermore, high rank managers have to be responsible for the success of their plans. These findings are in accordance with the argument made by Chen 2010, Ong and Ismail, 2008; De Cieri and Kramar, 2005 that human skill is the best predictor of utilizing the social media in the hotel industry. Useem, 1993 study was founded on the same approach which found a positive link between each dimension of human skill and social media utilization. The technology adoption level which influences its level of technology adoptions in which the commitment of top management should be higher in the hotel. Therefore, this study empirically found by identifying the substantially supporting evidence on the significance of the human skill being a prerequisite of utilization of social media.

The human skill was found to be a significant determinant for the competitive advantages as measured by the IT knowledge, top management commitment and the time spend on social media. The findings of this study emphasized that IT knowledge and top management commitments have a moderate positive relationship with the competitive advantage in the star hotels in Sri Lanka. Top management commitment as a human skill dimension makes a positive relationship with the organizational performance in which this study confirms to that human skill is a vital factor in focusing on the competitive advantages. This evidence by the study by Carpenter et al. (2004), where the role of top management of a firm includes the strategic decisions and its actions contain a force for the changing and development of the organization. According to Barney (1991), the top management in a business has to control the diversified resources for achieving the competitive advantage from a resource-based view which is direct to the financial performance in the short-run and long-run.

The study found empirical evidence to support that IT knowledge and experience positively and significantly impact on competitive advantage. This finding empirically confirms the theoretical arguments given by Drew (2003), Qureshi and York (2008). Therefore, this study empirically support by identifying the substantially supporting evidence on the significance of the human skill being a prerequisite of competitive advantage.

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